

Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 1

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 2

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 3

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 4

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 5

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 6

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 7

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 8

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 9

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 10

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 11

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 12

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 13

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 14

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 15

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 16

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Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 17

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 18

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 19

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 20

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 21

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 22

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 23

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 24

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 25

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 26

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 27

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 28

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 29

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 30

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 31

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 32

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 33

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 34

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 35

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 36

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 37

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 38

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 40

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 41

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 42

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 43

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B

Metric: NODF



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Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 44

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 45

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 46

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B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 47

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 48

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 49

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 50

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 51

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 52

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 53

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 54

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 55

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 56

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 57

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 58

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 59

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 60

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 61

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 62

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 63

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 64

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 65

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 66

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 67

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 68

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 69

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 70

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 71

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 72

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 73

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 74

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 75

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 76

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 77

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 78

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 79

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 80

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 81

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 82

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 83

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 84

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 85

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 86

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 87

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 90

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 91

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 92

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 93

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 94

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 95

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 96

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 97

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 98

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 99

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT



Source: theoretical-uniform

ID: 100

A



B

Metric: NODF



C

Metric: NT

